
Recent Trends in English Language and Literature

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Introduction

In the modern era of globalization, English language has become a language of mobility, power and language of science and technology. So far as communication is concerned English language has got tremendous importance at the international level. English language and literature are source of information because all the advanced knowledge of the world is available in English language and literature. The importance of English language and literature is above par at higher level of education. In olden days, English language and literature were taught with the help of traditional ways and methods. Now it is need of hour to update and alter traditional system of teaching and learning English language. Recent trends in English language and literature are innovative, creative, interesting, interactive and students oriented. Today the scenario of higher education with regard to English teaching is changed from the traditional aspect. Doff says, “A look back over time show that language teaching and learners alike have often moved between these two orientations and that in many cases teaches and learning as like have tried to strike a balance between the two poles”(Doff 2018)

Grammar Translation Method, Direct or Natural Method, Dr. West’s New Method, Bilingual method, The Audio lingual Method, Suggestopedia, The Silent

Way Total Physical Response Method, Communicative Method, Lecture Method, Seminar Method and Discussion Method these are traditional method’s of teaching and learning English language and literature. With the passage of time the above method’s are out dated. Even the National Policy of Education provides people with an opportunity to think on the critical, social, economic, cultural, moral and spiritual issues of humanity. English language and literature learning is a very complex process and even eminent scholars could not evolve any perfect formula and method regarding the process because the form and status of English language and literature has been changing with the passage of time. So recent trends, method’s and approaches are introduced and implemented in teaching and learning process of English language and literature.

Recent Trends in English Language and Literature:

1. Computer based Technology:

As a recent in English language and literature is computer based technology. According to Becker 2000, computers are regarded as an important instructional instrument in language classes in which teachers have convenient access, are sufficiently prepared and have some freedom in the curriculum. Computer technology is regarded by a lot of teachers to

be a significant part of providing a high-quality education. It also provides unlimited resources to English languages learners. By using computer based language activities improve cooperative learning in learners. Computer based activities in language provide rapid information and appropriate materials By using computer based technology many authentic materials can be provided to teachers and they can be motivated in learning English language. If the teachers will not use technology in their teaching they will lag behind in the future. So it is need of hours that the English teachers should possess full knowledge of technology. Computer aided teaching makes the learning enjoyable and motivates learners in learning demand active participation, keep the learners vigilant saves the learners time and provides a better learning environment. As computer is used in various field, the scientists and researchers belived in computer and they claim that no teaches ever born, no method ever utilised, can match the computer efficiency. Due to increasing importance of computer the students, the future citizens and employees of various fields have adopted computer as a recent trend of teaching and learning English language and literature.

2. Information and communication Technology:

Now a days ICT has become one of the most effective trends in English language and Literature It is a technological tool and resource which is used to communicate, create, remove, store and manage information. ICT includes Radio, TV, Computer, Internet services, hardware, software recording and processing system for sound, still and moving picture. Traditional methods of teaching are students oriented but the modern techniques of teaching emphasises on student oriented approach. ICT is essential to master the basic skills and concepts and plays an

important role in changing and modernizing educational systems and way of learning The curricula of English language and literature also has focused on the practical and experience oriented aspects of life.

The progress of science and technology have brought innovative, creative and effective trend in English language and literature. ICT has made remarkable contribution in searching of solution and in the methodology of language teaching and learning. The advancement of ICT has a vast share in the growth of English language. ICT promotes a self determined learning instrument and it also creat interest among the learners. It makes the learners more comfortable in the class room. Up to date information of any particular subject is freely available. Live conversation between teachers and students is possible It makes complex process easier to understand. ICT presents an entirely new learning environment for student's. Hence keeping in mind the importance of ICT, the former president of India, late Dr. A.P.J Abdul Kalam had stated that, India can be one of the developed countries in the world by 2020 if technology is adopted as a tool and the teching community should change the mindset and encourage the students by means of technology.

3. Recent Trends in teaching English Language and Literature:

1.The world wide web, 2.Nicenet, 3.Y.Blogs for video based materials, 4.Podcasts, 5.Blog, 6.Designing Websites, 7.Electronic pen friends, 8.Youtube, 9.E-mail, 10.Website, 11.Skype, 12. Power point presentation and mobile, 13.Twitter, 14. E-learning technology, 15.E-Resources 16.E-Journals, 17. Virtual class room, 18.Vedio conferencing, 19. Satellite based education, 20. Interactive whiteboards and smart boards.

The above recent trends are very effective in teaching and learning process of English language and literature. The features

of the above multimedia resources like sound, picture, animations and colours take the students closer to real life and make the students able to communicate more effectively, practice language skills thoroughly and solve language learning problem easily. In the teaching of English language and literature at under graduate level, the multimedia resources are used when the subject matter is complex and difficult to explain, materials is quite lengthy to introduce and develop a lesson to create real life situation motivate students to develop interest and to explain the idea in a better way. The use of above technology in the field of education is the reform of twenty first century. The modern educational technology provide ample scope to the teachers as well as students to make the teaching learning process of English language and literature more effective. The multimedia also promotes interactive English language learning. This also supports to the project based language learning and teaching and helps to improve the standard of English and the students become able to communicate in English. The teachers also realize the significance of technology in English language teaching and strongly advocate the use of multimedia.

4. E-learning and E- resources technology:

E learning Technology and E - resource is one of the recent and emerging trends in teaching and learning process of English language and literature. E- learning technology enables to learn through communication, interaction and collaboration It is collaborative learning process in which people learn from one another and exchange the views with peer group. E-learning technology makes the learning process individual based rather than institutional based. Though E-learning can not be replaced to classroom teaching and learning but if blended can produce excellent results. The E- learning tools are changing

the world. New applications of E- learning encompasses radio and television. New digital technologies like overhead projector, interactive boards, i-pods ,blogs, computer, internet, cameras, audio equipement, printers, e-mail, videoconferencing and many supports the teaching learning process of English language and literature. Bernard Luskin, a pioneer of E-learning, advocates that the ‘e’ means exciting energetic, enthusiastic, emotional, extended and excellent education in addition to electronic. For many students E-learning is the most convenient way to pursue a degree in higher education. Many students are working and battling with serious illness and it became difficult for such students to find time to attend college in the schedule such students are more motivated to enroll in an E-learning class.

E-resources are available 24/7 or whenever used wants to access. The university of Glassgrow delivers the term, E-Resources as many resources that are available over the internet can be called an. E- resources “The resources available on internet are known as E- resources, through which, users can find and locate the right information at the right time in the right form Surwade 116.” E resources are used more than one user provides timely access allows remote access supports different searching capabilities and supports multimedia information It has created a new place in the world of communication and information sharing. The new opportunity is endowed for users authors and publishers to share as well as collect information. Less physical space is required for storing information, easy to use, automatic updating, better for distant users and easy to download Digital textbook, E-journals, virtual classroom, video-conferencing satellite based education interactive whiteboards and smart boards ect are means of E-resources.

Conclusion:

The traditional methods of teaching English language and literature and Recent trends and technology based methods both things can not be said as best ones and can not be justified and answered. Teaching English language and literature as a foreign language with the help of technology tools might not again all the benefits we expect and the changes which are required in the modern world cause the presence of a teacher in the classroom is the basic tool of change. Technology intervention should be taken as a positive change and be used hand in hand traditional methodologies of teaching English language and literature It is also proved that no technology can replace a teacher who stands as a companion with his learners and takes care of conditioning of young minds. In the end it can be said that technology based trends in teaching English language and literature as a foreign language can be seen only if the learners have accepted it completely and benefitted completely.

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